

Associations between Joint Attention and Language in Autism Spectrum Disorder and Typical
Development: A Systematic Review and Meta-Regression Analysis

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Lay Abstract

This study used a systematic search and meta-analysis procedures to synthesize existing research reporting associations between joint attention and language. In meta-analysis, associations are referred to as an *effect size*. The purpose of the study was to determine if variability in effect sizes could be explained by ‘moderator’ variables. The two moderator variables that were of particular interest were group (typically developing [TD] children or children with autism spectrum disorder [ASD]) and the type of joint attention that was measured. Joint attention types included responding to joint attention (RJA), and ‘other’; a collapsed variable that included four other types of joint attention. Meta-regression was used to determine which factors remained significant when moderators were entered together in a single statistical model. Analyses were conducted separately for expressive language, receptive language, and composite language variables (expressive and receptive measures combined together). For expressive and receptive language, effect sizes were higher in groups with ASD, and when RJA was the joint attention variable. For composite language, none of the moderators were significant. An interpretation for these results is that, for TD children, joint attention occurs at high enough thresholds that language development is no longer tied to variation in joint attention. In children with ASD, joint attention may fall below this critical threshold, so language levels are more dependent on joint attention levels. Further, these results suggest that RJA may be more highly associated with language as compared to other types of joint attention.

Scientific Abstract

Using a structured literature search and meta-regression procedures, this study sought to determine whether associations between joint attention and language are moderated by group (autism spectrum disorder [ASD] vs. typical development [TD]), joint attention type (responding to joint attention [RJA] vs. other), and other study design features and participant characteristics. Studies were located using database searches, hand searches, and electronic requests for data from experts in the field. This resulted in 71 reports or datasets and 605 effect sizes, representing 1,859 participants with ASD and 1,835 TD participants. Meta-regression was used to answer research questions regarding potential moderators of the effect sizes of interest, which were Pearson's r values quantifying the association between joint attention and language variables. In the final models, conducted separately for each language variable, effect sizes were significantly higher for the ASD group as compared to the TD group, and for RJA as compared to non-RJA joint attention types. Approximate mental age trended toward significance for the expressive language model. Joint attention may be more tightly tied to language in children with ASD as compared to TD children because TD children exhibit joint attention at sufficient thresholds so that language development becomes untethered to variations in joint attention. Conversely, children with ASD who exhibit deficits in joint attention develop language contingent upon their joint attention abilities. Because RJA was more strongly related to language than other types of joint attention, future research should involve careful consideration of the operationalization and measurement of joint attention constructs.

Keywords: Autism spectrum disorder; Joint attention; Language; Meta-Analysis

Associations between Joint Attention and Language in Autism Spectrum Disorder and Typical Development: A Systematic Review and Meta-Regression Analysis

The concept of joint attention has been fundamental to investigators seeking to understand the processes involved in language development. The coinage of the term *joint attention* is credited to Jerome Bruner, who delineated the social attention aspects of joint attention as distinct from, and ontogenetically prior to language (Bruner, 1975 cited in Mundy & Jarrold, 2010). Joint attention routines allow for recurrent episodes of mutual attention to objects and events of interest, which provide a context for the child to associate language with its referent (Tomasello & Farrar, 1986). The joint attention construct has maintained an especially important role in research on children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), since approximately a quarter of these children do not develop functional language, an outcome thought to be rooted in joint attention impairments (Sigman & Ruskin, 1999; Tager-Flusberg, Paul, & Lord, 2005). Joint attention difficulties are among the earliest indicators of ASD (Werner & Dawson, 2005), discriminate children with and without ASD (Shumway & Wetherby, 2009), and predict ASD symptoms in adulthood (Gillespie-Lynch, Sepeta, Wang, Marshall, Gomez, Sigman, & Hutman, 2012).

Far from a monolithic construct, joint attention comprises several distinct variations that have been defined differently, but in some cases used interchangeably, over more than 30 years of research on this topic (Yoder & McDuffie, 2006). Common to all joint attention variables is the triadic sharing of attention between a child and another person (almost always an adult) around an object or event. Joint attention behaviors first emerge in TD children around 6 months

of age, and are consolidated into brief episodes of sustained joint engagement around 9 months of age (Bakeman & Adamson, 1984). Developmental theory posits that symbolic language develops out of these early sharing experiences that are scaffolded by caregivers (Bakeman & Adamson, 1984). First words follow the onset of joint attention at around 12-18 months, and more complex language forms appear by 30 months of age (Bates, 1979).

It is important to carefully distinguish between joint attention constructs since they are thought to develop along distinct paths, and to differentially impact language development (Adamson, Bakeman, Deckner, & Ronski, 2009; Bakeman & Adamson, 1984; Mundy & Jarrold, 2010). While many joint attention constructs rely on similar behavioral evidence, they are measured in different ways that may tap different developmental achievements. For the present analysis, five constructs are included under the broad umbrella of joint attention; coordinated attention (CA), initiating joint attention (IJA), responding to joint attention (RJA), supported joint engagement (SJE), and coordinated joint engagement (CJE). Each construct is briefly described below, along with research describing contributions to language development.

Responding to Joint Attention

RJA refers to the child's propensity to respond, usually with gaze, to social bids for attention from an interaction partner. Bids can include points, spoken language, or more subtle forms such as gaze direction. Toddlers with ASD show decreased responsivity to social bids for attention as compared to TD toddlers (Chawarska, Macari, & Schic, 2012), which may indicate that an automatic state of 'readiness' for social interaction that is dampened in children with ASD. RJA is a robust predictor of both receptive and expressive language in children with ASD, even after controlling for other known predictors of language (Yoder, Watson, & Lambert,

2014). Further, this association remains statistically significant even when there is a lag of several years between measures of RJA and language (Sigman & McGovern, 2005).

Coordinated Attention

Coordinated attention refers to the child's ability to shift attention between a person and an object or event of mutual interest, without the adult prompting a response, or cuing a social interaction bid by expectantly gazing at the child. The extent to which children with ASD and TD differ on this measure of joint attention has not yet been tested, but research has identified longitudinal relationships between coordinated attention and expressive and receptive language in children with ASD (Charman, 2003). Interestingly, these associations remained significant even when mental age is partialled out, indicating that the relationship cannot be explained by general cognitive abilities.

Initiating Joint Attention

IJA involves intentional overtures from the child to the interaction partner, in order to establish attention for the purpose of sharing affect or interest about an object or event (Yoder & McDuffie, 2006). Bids can include multiple modalities, such as gaze, gesture, or spoken language. Research has shown that IJA is impaired in children with ASD (Wetherby, Watt, Morgan, and Shumway, 2007), and that initiating for social purposes is more significantly impaired than initiations for non-social purposes, such as regulating others' behavior or making requests (Stone, Ousley, Yoder, Hogan, & Hepburn, 1997). IJA appears to be a clear predictor of concurrent receptive and expressive language in children with ASD, but its role in later language development is less clear, as research has sometimes failed to find longitudinal associations between IJA and language (Gillespie-Lynch et al., 2012; Sigman & McGovern, 2005; Toth, Munson, Meltzoff, & Dawson, 2006).

Supported and Coordinated Joint Engagement

Whereas the prior three constructs represent the behavioral propensities of the child, the final two joint attention types are dyadic variables that capture the interactive work of the parent in collaboration with the child. These constructs are demonstrated by an extended series of interactional turns, rather than more discrete behavioral overtures. In SJE the parent and child are engaged with the same symbol or object, and the child does not actively reference the adult with gaze. In CJE, the parent and child are similarly engaged with the same symbol or object, but the child gives explicit attention to the adult at key moments within the episode. Children with ASD show lower levels of CJE than typically developing children, and SJE predicts language for children with ASD and TD children (Adamson, Bakeman, Deckner, & Ronski, 2009; Bakeman & Adamson, 1984).

The Current Study

Surprisingly, despite the large amount of research examining the effects of joint attention (in all its forms) on language, there have been no attempts to synthesize and sort out this literature using a meta-analytic approach. There are also no single studies that examine two pressing questions, which constitute the first two aims of this study: 1) whether there are differences in associations between joint attention and language by type of joint attention construct, and 2) whether associations differ for ASD as compared to TD populations. There are several studies that have examined pairs of joint attention types against each other, but none have attempted to examine all five. For example, SJE has been found to be a superior predictor of language as compared to CJE, when caregivers provide linguistic input during the engagement states (Adamson et al., 2009; Bakeman & Adamson, 1984). Adamson and colleagues suggest the reduced cognitive requirements of SJE free up mental resources for matching linguistic

references to their objects (Bakeman & Adamson, 1984). Similarly, RJA has been shown to be superior to IJA in several studies (Bono, Daley, & Sigman, 2004; Dawson et al., 2004; Sigman & McGovern, 2005; summarized in Mundy & Jarrold, 2010). RJA may tap an early propensity for a child to socially orient to others, which provides for maximal language learning opportunities (Jones & Klin, 2013; Mundy & Jarrold, 2010).

Although there are currently no published studies that have directly tested differences in associations between joint attention and language between groups of children with ASD and TD children, some studies have found significant associations for ASD groups while failing to find associations for TD groups (Gillespie-Lynch et al., 2015; Maljaars, Noens, Jansen, Scholte, & van Berckelaer-Onnes, 2011). It has also repeatedly been demonstrated that children with ASD have joint attention deficits as compared to TD children (Adamson et al., 2009; Shumway & Wetherby, 2009). One interpretation of these two sets of findings is that TD children engage in sufficiently high levels of joint attention, ensuring that language develops regardless of any variability beyond this threshold. Therefore, associations between joint attention and language would be expected to be higher in children with ASD as compared to TD children. The current study sought to determine if this is indeed the case. A final aim was to determine if the above putative moderators (JA type and group) remain significant after potentially important features of participants (approximate mental age, percent male) and studies (year of publication, time to follow-up) are accounted for.

This study used structured literature search and meta-analytic procedures in order to synthesize extant research on associations between joint attention and three language variables; expressive, receptive, and composite language. Language variables were considered separately, since there is evidence that receptive and expressive language are at least partially disassociated,

especially in children with ASD (Pickles, Anderson, & Lord, 2014; Woynaroski, Yoder, & Watson, 2015). Meta-regression was used to determine if effect sizes vary according to the moderators¹ of interest (i.e., group, joint attention type, sample characteristics, and study characteristics). In sum, the following research questions were examined:

1. Are effect sizes for the association between joint attention and language moderated by joint attention type, within each group and language type?
2. Are effect sizes for associations between joint attention and language moderated by group (ASD vs. TD), within each language type?
3. Which putative moderators of effect sizes for the association between joint attention and language, including joint attention type, group, approximate mental age, and study features account for unique variance in effect size estimates, when included together in meta-regressions within each language type?

Method

Search Procedures

Several search methods were employed to retrieve relevant effect sizes. The main search method was through electronic databases, including ERIC, PsycINFO, and ProQuest Dissertations and Theses. Reports that were published between 1970 and 2015 were gathered. Search terms included combinations of autism, autism spectrum disorder, ASD, association, correlation, predict, joint attention, joint engagement, language, receptive, expressive, and social communication. The *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* and *Child Development* were hand searched. Additional efforts were made to locate unpublished findings or ‘gray

¹ In meta-regression, the term ‘moderator’ refers to variables entered as predictors in a meta-regression model, not as variables entered as interaction terms as in traditional regression. In this sense, ‘moderator’ and ‘predictor’ are somewhat interchangeable in a meta-regression context (Borenstein et al., 2009).

literature', to ensure a representative sample not skewed in favor of significant effect sizes (i.e., the 'file-drawer' problem; Scargle, 2000). These efforts involved online searches through recent conference proceedings for the *International Meeting for Autism Research* (2006-2014) and the *Society for Research on Child Development* (2005-2013). This search generated an email list of 199 researchers who were contacted to request published or unpublished data relevant to the search.

Inclusion Criteria

Reports were selected if they met the following criteria: (1) published after 1970, (2) written in English, (3) included a group of participants diagnosed with a confirmed diagnosis of ASD per DSM criteria (confirmation could occur after data collection occurred, as long as analysis was only conducted on the later confirmed participants) and/or a separate group of typically developing participants not at risk for a developmental disorder, and (4) included measures of joint attention and language (defined below) so that either longitudinal or concurrent associations, with joint attention measured first, could be calculated. There were no restrictions on the chronological or mental age of participants. For studies that included measures of interest but did not report Pearson's r or partial r , authors were contacted to request this information. See Figure 1 for the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flow diagram of located studies.

[place Figure 1 about here]

Coding the Studies

Included reports and unpublished datasets were coded according to a detailed manual².

² Available from the author upon request

Report-level features included: year published, whether or not the report was from a published or unpublished source, and whether or not the report indicated that it shared a sample with any other published report. *Effect-size-level features* included the following:

1. Sample size
2. Group (ASD or TD)
3. Mental age (derived from IQ and chronological age if not reported directly, using the equation $MA = [\text{Chron. Age} * IQ]/100$)
4. Chronological age
5. Percent male
6. Joint attention variable type
 - a. CA: three point gaze shifts between objects of mutual attention and an interaction partner, without adult prompting
 - b. IJA: Communicative acts to initiate interaction with another person around an object or event, for the purpose of sharing affect or interest (excludes initiations to regulate others behavior or make a request).
 - c. RJA: Responses to bids for joint attention from others.
 - d. CJE: A state in which the child and parent are actively involved with the same object or event, and the child actively acknowledges the parent's participation, usually with gaze at key moments in the interaction.
 - e. SJE: A state in which the child and parent are actively involved with the same object or event, but the child does not acknowledge the parent's participation with eye contact. The parent's involvement influences the child's activity with the object.

7. Time-to follow up: number of months between joint attention and language assessments
8. Procedure to confirm diagnosis (for ASD effect sizes only)
9. Type of effect size (Pearson's r or partial r)
10. Language variable type
 - a. Expressive: Spoken language including lexical size, mean length of utterance, or structural language features
 - b. Receptive: Understanding of spoken language, including receptive vocabulary size
 - c. Composite: Aggregate of expressive and receptive language, or variables that tap both expressive and receptive abilities (for example, pragmatics as measured by the *Children's Communication Checklist*)
11. Value of the correlation coefficient (r or partial r) for the association between joint attention and language

All primary coding was completed by the author. A doctoral-level graduate student randomly selected and coded 31% of reports selected after initial screening to estimate inter-rater reliability. Coders agreed on exclusion/inclusion 93% of the time, and disagreements were resolved by consensus. Coders overlapped on 29% of studies that were selected for inclusion by at least one coder. For continuous variables, the average ICC was .90 (range .77- .99), indicating very good agreement (Yoder & Symons, 2010). For categorical variables, agreement was 90% (Range = 89-91%).

Putative Moderators

Group (ASD vs. TD) and joint attention type (IJA, RJA, CA, SJE, and CJE) were the primary moderators of interest, but other putative moderators were also examined to determine if

they accounted for heterogeneity in effect sizes. These include study or design features (year of study and time to follow-up) and characteristics of the samples (approximate mental age and percent male).

After coding was completed, it was clear that studies involving exclusively TD participants tended not to report a mean mental age (MA), a putative moderator. Studies involving participants with ASD were more likely to provide mean MAs, but some only reported verbal mental age (VMA) or nonverbal mental age (NVMA). Thus, a collapsed category was created combining these variables in order to maximize the ability to test moderation by ‘approximate mental age’. This category used mean mental age for ASD groups when available, and mean chronological age for all TD groups under the assumption that mean chronological age and mean MA should be similar in typically developing samples. If mean mental age was not reported for ASD samples, VMA (3 studies) or NVMA (2 studies) was used. If neither of these were reported, chronological age was used (5 studies).

Statistical Procedures

The effect size of interest for this analysis is the Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation (r) calculated for associations between language and joint attention variables. Partial correlations were also included. Since the variance of correlation coefficients are dependent on the size of the correlation, this study followed the standard meta-analytic procedure of Fisher’s z transforming effect sizes prior to analysis (Borenstein, Hedges, Higgins, & Rothstein, 2009). Effect sizes were then back-transformed to Pearson’s r for reporting results.

Most of the included studies contributed multiple effect sizes. Further, 13 of the reports selected for inclusion shared some or all participants with at least one other report. This violates the assumption of independence required by traditional meta-analysis procedures. Ignoring this

dependency would result in underestimating standard errors, which elevates Type I errors (Hedges, Tipton, & Johnson, 2010). Prior meta-analysts have dealt with this issue by either selecting a single ‘best’ effect size from each study, or averaging together all eligible effect sizes (Tanner-Smith & Tipton, 2014). These procedures are unsatisfactory for the present analysis for several reasons. First, several of the moderator analyses would be more difficult or impossible under this approach, as it would require averaging across, for example, the different lengths of time to follow-up within a study, which is a moderator of interest. Second, the criterion by which one selects a single ‘best’ effect size is often arbitrary, and can bias results (if one were to select the largest effect size, for example). Selecting a single effect size also runs counter to the arduous work undertaken in the gray literature search which seeks to gather *all* effect sizes precisely in order to avoid biasing results.

To circumvent these issues, this analysis utilized the robust variance estimation (RVE) approach to meta-analysis and meta-regression using the ROBUMETA macro in Stata (StataCorp, 2013). RVE accounts for clustering of effect sizes within studies (Hedges, Tipton, & Johnson, 2010; Tanner-Smith & Tipton, 2014). An effect size is modeled as:

$$T_{ij} = \beta_1 X_{1ij} + \beta_2 X_{2ij} + \dots + \beta_p X_{p ij} + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

Where i indicates the effect size and j indicates the study or cluster. As in traditional ordinary least squares (OLS) regression, the predictors (or moderators in this case) $X_{1ij} \dots X_{p ij}$ account for variation in the effect size T_{ij} to some degree.

Random weights were used in the RVE analyses, since the primary dependency in the retrieved effect sizes was nesting of multiple effect sizes within a study (see Tanner-Smith & Tipton, 2014 for a description of weight types). In the RVE approach, an estimate of the mean correlation (ρ) between all pairs of effect sizes in a given cluster is used to estimate τ^2 , the

between-study sampling variance (Tanner-Smith, Wilson, & Lipsey, 2013). By default, Stata assigns ρ a value of 1.0, but sensitivity tests were conducted to ensure that findings were robust across reasonable estimates of ρ (i.e., .10- .90). This approach calculates weights (w) for each effect size i within each study j as:

$$w_{ij} = 1 / \{ (V_{\bullet j} + \tau^2) [1 + (k_j - 1)\rho] \}$$

where $V_{\bullet j}$ is the within-study mean of the sampling variances for each study j , τ^2 is the between-studies variance component estimate, k_j is the number of effect sizes within each study j , and the constant ρ indicates the assumed correlation between all pairs of observed effect sizes within each study.

A series of meta-regression models were conducted to answer each research question. In addition to separate regressions for expressive and receptive language variables, ‘composite language’ was included as a third outcome. This variable involves measures of expressive and receptive language combined together (represented by 54 of the effect sizes in our dataset). The decision to include this outcome variable was primarily to avoid excluding this important research.

First, a set of unconditional models were implemented by language type and group to determine the overall effect of joint attention on expressive, receptive, and composite language measures for ASD and TD groups separately. Second, meta-regressions by each joint attention type, again within language outcome and group, were conducted to calculate summary effects further broken down by joint attention category. Forest plots were constructed using the results of these two sets of analyses, to determine whether there were significant differences (i.e., non-overlapping confidence intervals) by joint attention type. Simple meta-regressions were then conducted with remaining potential continuous (year of publication, approximate mental age at

the initial time point, time to follow-up, and percent of male participants) and categorical (group) moderators of interest entered separately. Significant moderators were then entered into a single regression model for each language outcome to determine which variables predicted unique variance in effect sizes. To determine the extent of publication bias, a final set of regression models were implemented with source (published or unpublished) entered as a moderator.

Results

The structured search yielded a total of 605 effect sizes, which represented 1,859 participants with ASD and 1,835 TD participants. There was an average of 8.3 effect sizes from each report/dataset (Range = 1-68). A total of 24 reports (23 independent participant samples) and 273 effect sizes (45%) were gathered from unpublished sources. Percent male was reported for 83% of studies for at least one participant group, and 100% of studies reported either chronological age or some aspect of mental age. In terms of procedures to measure joint attention, 69% of effect sizes involved an examiner-child interaction session, 29% involved a parent-child interaction session, 1.4% involved a parent report, and < 1% involved a classroom session. For measuring language, 55% involved a clinical assessment with an examiner, 43% of effect sizes involved a parent report, 1.5% involved a clinical assessment with a a parent, and < 1% involved a combination of assessment types. A description of each included report is presented in Table 1. Means and standard deviations of participant and study characteristics are presented in Table 2.

Preliminary Analyses

In order to determine if mean sample and study characteristics differed between studies collected on TD participants and ASD participants, a series of independent means t-tests were conducted. Results indicated that there were statistically significant differences in approximate

mental age and percent male in samples of children with ASD as compared to TD samples ($p < .001$ in both cases). The approximate MAs of children with ASD tended to be greater than CAs of TD children (recall that CA for TD children is a proxy for MA, given that most studies on TD samples did not report MA), and ASD samples had higher percentages of male participants. Mean time to follow-up and year of publication did not differ between the two groups.

A preliminary meta-regression was conducted to determine if partial r effect sizes ($n = 50$) differed from r effect sizes. The average mean difference was small (-0.02) and not statistically significant ($p = 0.85$). Therefore, effect sizes were combined for all subsequent analyses. Forest plots for estimates of correlations by language outcome and group are presented in Figure 2. This figure provides estimates for individual joint attention types, as well as overall estimates collapsed across joint attention types within each language outcome and group. Effect size estimates collapsed across joint attention variables range from $.22$ to $.47$, which are considered weak to strong positive relationships (Cohen, 1988).

Moderator Analyses by Group and Joint Attention Type

With the exception of composite language for the TD group, the number of clusters (k) exceeded the recommended 10 studies for generating summary effect sizes (Tanner-Smtih & Tipton, 2014). Because the number of clusters reporting effect sizes for composite language in TD samples was small ($k = 2$) the confidence intervals around the summary estimate are quite large and should be interpreted with caution. The remaining summary estimates (collapsed across joint attention type) are significantly larger than zero.

There were too few studies examining correlations between joint attention and composite language scores in TD samples to generate summary effects broken down by joint attention type. For several joint attention types, including CJE-ASD, SJE-ASD, and CA-ASD within receptive

language, and SJE-ASD and SJE-TD within expressive language, cluster sizes were 5 or fewer, resulting in wide confidence intervals and untrustworthy p -values. All of the remaining confidence intervals did not overlap with zero, and were in the positive direction. Within each language and group, there were no pairs of effect sizes for joint attention types with non-overlapping confidence intervals.

[place Figure 2 about here]

Meta-Regressions

Prior to conducting meta-regressions for the remaining putative moderators, continuous variables were transformed in two ways. First, approximate mental age and time to follow-up were natural log transformed, since these variables showed evidence of skewness. Second, because time to follow-up varied both within and between clusters, two new variables were created to separate out these effects, as recommended by Tanner-Smith and Tipton (2014). A cluster mean variable was created to model between-cluster effects, and a cluster mean-centered variable was created to model within-cluster effects. Results of simple meta-regressions for the remaining putative moderators of effect size are given in Table 3. Percent male and approximate mental age were significant moderators of expressive language. None of these potential moderators reached significance for receptive or composite language.

[place Table 3 about here]

Significant categorical and continuous moderators were then combined into three separate meta-regression models for each language outcome. Group was included in expressive language and receptive language meta-regressions, but there were too few effect sizes for TD samples within the composite language outcome to include this as a moderator. Since entering all five joint attention types into a single model was not feasible given insufficient numbers of effect

sizes within each type, only RJA was also included to determine if this particular category of joint attention variable was significantly different from the other types combined. RJA was chosen because it tended to have the highest point estimate across language outcomes, there were a sufficiently large number of clusters for this variable to generate a reliable summary effect, and prior research suggests that it may be the most robust predictor of language (Mundy & Jarrold, 2010). Percent male was not included in the final expressive language meta-regression model despite its significance in the unconditional model for several reasons. First, as can be seen in Table 3, the coefficient in the simple meta-regression for this variable was close to zero. This indicates that while statistically significant, the effect of this variable was negligible. Second, the degrees of freedom in a multiple meta-regression model that included this variable were too small to generate trustworthy p values (this occurs when degrees of freedom are less than 4). Lastly, percent male was highly intercorrelated with group (polychoric $\rho = .79$), since effect sizes with high percentages of males tended to involve samples with ASD. To protect against collinearity, percent male was omitted from the final model.

Results indicated that, for expressive language, group was a significant moderator, and approximate mental age and RJA trended toward significance when using two-tailed tests ($p = .07$ for both). After it became clear that the initial analysis plan was not feasible, and a single JA type would need to be selected to test against the others, RJA was chosen because it was hypothesized to be the strongest positive moderator of effect sizes. Thus, one-tailed tests are reported as well, which indicate significance ($p = .035$). For receptive language, both group and RJA were significant moderators. For composite language, only RJA was entered into the model, and it did not reach significance. The τ^2 estimates (an indicator of the between study variance)

for each model range from .04 to .07, indicating the remaining variability in effect sizes not accounted for by the models is small. The full results are given in Table 4.

[place Table 4 about here]

Publication Bias

The final series of meta-regression models sought to determine if effect sizes retrieved from published as compared to unpublished sources were significantly different (i.e., to determine the extent of publication bias). For both receptive and expressive language, unpublished effect sizes tended to be smaller, but the coefficient was not significant in either model ($p = .33$ and $.10$, respectively). There were too few unpublished effect sizes to examine this effect for composite language, but it is unlikely that the effect of publication source would be different for this language outcome. Because an extensive gray literature search resulted in the retrieval of a high percentage of effect sizes that were unpublished and publication status was not a significant moderator, it is unlikely that the results of this analysis reflect publication bias.

Discussion

This meta-regression analysis used robust variance estimation to synthesize research on the associations between joint attention and language in individuals with ASD and TD, and identify significant moderators of effect sizes. Summary effect sizes ranged from weak to strong, depending on language outcome and group. Group and RJA were significant moderators of expressive language effect sizes (when a one-tailed test was used for the latter), and mental age trended toward significance. Group and RJA were significant moderators of receptive language effect sizes.

Limitations

Prior to discussing results, the limitations of the study should be considered. First, given that Pearson's r is an index of correlation, it is not possible to conclude a *causal* relationship between joint attention and language. Second, there are other variables not considered here that could explain differences in associations between joint attention and language, such as severity of ASD symptoms or maternal education (which were not frequently reported in the retrieved studies). Future research should report these potentially moderating variables to make such analyses possible. Third, the ASD and TD groups were not matched on key variables such as percent male and approximate mental age, potentially confounding the results. However, these concerns are alleviated by the fact that these variables were controlled for in the combined models when found to be significant in simple meta-regressions. Fourth, there were too few effect sizes to adequately generate confidence intervals and run individual moderator analyses for several joint attention variables, including CJE, SJE, and CA. Fifth, this meta-analysis primarily measured relationships between joint attention and expressive and receptive vocabulary size. This is because the majority of studies were conducted on young children, and vocabulary size is the most appropriate indicator of language development for this age group (Tager-Flusberg et al., 2009). Future research on older children should examine associations between joint attention and other aspects of language, such as structural or pragmatic features (Gillespie-Lynch et al., 2015 for example). Finally, meta-regression can yield false-positive findings if conducted with few studies, use fixed-effects approaches, and involve many covariates (Higgins & Thompson, 2004). The final models conducted in the current study involved many studies (i.e., ≥ 40 for the final meta-regression models, except for composite language in which no significant effects were found), and used random effects. However, the

number of covariates tested is greater than five, which could increase the likelihood of spurious findings.

Group as a Moderator of Effect Sizes

For the first research question regarding the differences in summary effect sizes for ASD and TD groups within each language outcome, the study hypotheses were partially confirmed. Effect sizes were significantly higher in ASD groups for expressive and receptive language, but it was not possible to calculate the effects of an ASD diagnosis for composite language due to too few studies. It is this author's understanding that this is a novel finding that was not directly tested in any of the individual studies comprising this analysis. One interpretation of this finding is that there is a threshold of joint attention, exhibited by all TD children and some children with ASD, that once met will result in expressive and receptive language development that is no longer tethered to variation in joint attention. Since children with ASD generally fall below this threshold and exhibit diminished joint attention, their language is more contingent on joint attention abilities. In support of this view, Toth and colleagues (2004) have suggested that joint attention may be part of a 'starter set' of abilities that are essential in setting the stage for language development, but are then supplanted by other developmental achievements that drive further growth. TD children may reach threshold levels of joint attention more quickly than children with ASD, making it less relevant for continued language development. This hypothesis could be tested with procedures such as polynomial regression, using data collected for children with a range of joint attention abilities and determining the point at which associations between joint attention and language begin to decline.

Joint Attention Type as a Moderator of Effect Sizes

The second research question considered whether effect sizes differed by the five identified joint attention types. This hypothesis was not fully confirmed, as there were no pairs of effect sizes that did not overlap within each language group, when ASD and TD groups were considered separately. However, in the combined meta-regression analyses, RJA was a significant moderator of receptive language, and was also a significant moderator of expressive language when using a one-tailed test of significance. Thus, there is support for the hypothesis that RJA is a superior predictor of associations as compared to ‘non-RJA’ measures of joint attention. A possible explanation for this finding is that, within the measurement context, opportunities for RJA are more heavily structured by the examiner as compared to other joint attention variables. A typical measure of RJA involves a set number of social bids performed by the examiner, and the researcher then calculates either a proportion or raw frequency of instances where the child responds to those bids. IJA, on the other hand, involves spontaneous bids from the child that could be more sensitive to variations in toys, the child’s familiarity with the toys, or the skill of the examiner. SJE and CJE could be even less stable, as they are often measured in semi-structured or free play sessions, and depend largely on the contributions of the interaction partner. This might result in more stable estimates of RJA and reduced Type I errors, as compared to estimates of IJA (Yoder & Symons, 2010). These features of the measurement session introduce variability that is unrelated to the construct of interest, and makes it less likely that significant associations will be found when there is a true association (Bottema-Beutel, Lloyd, Carter, & Asmus, 2013).

Alternatively, it is possible that the superiority of RJA as a moderator of effect sizes is not due to measurement practices, but instead due to an actual advantage of RJA in the developmental course of expressive and receptive language. Neural systems that are overlapping

but substantially different may offer a biological explanation for the divergent importance of RJA as compared to other joint attention types (see Mundy & Jarrold 2010 for a review). Evidence that ASD involves a failure to automatically orient to social cues at an early age supports this theoretical position (Dawson, Bernier, & Ring, 2012; Mundy & Jarrold, 2010). RJA may index the child's propensity to view others as collaborators in social activities, and important sources of information about the world that warrant attention (Tomassello, 2008). Once a caregiver has secured their child's attention, additional linguistic interaction can ensue. If children with ASD do not display this automatic response to bids for attention, they then lose out on social experiences that are critical to language development. Lastly, children who exhibit high levels of RJA might have greater aptitude for processing linguistic input that is not tailored to their current focus of attention. It has repeatedly been demonstrated that parent utterances that follow the child's attentional focus is correlated with language development in children with ASD (McDuffie & Yoder, 2010). A propensity to respond to language bids of an adult, regardless of whether bids reflect the child's current state of attention, may broaden the range of adult linguistic input that influences the child's language development.

Significant Moderators after Controlling for Study and Sample Features

The combined meta-regression models confirmed that the ASD group showed higher associations between joint attention and language as compared to TD groups, even when RJA and, in the case of expressive language, approximate mental age were included in the model. Several potential moderators were not significant, including time-to-follow-up, which indicates that the associations between joint attention and language remain stable regardless of the time lapse between the two variables. In expressive language, the associations may increase with mental age. It is important to consider that the mean age of participants at first measurement was

quite young. Mundy & Jarrold (2010) have pointed out that children with ASD appear to make gains in RJA in later childhood, even if they remain nonverbal. Therefore, it is possible that associations do not maintain if the initial measure of RJA is measured beyond the preschool period.

Implications for Research and Practice

The results of this meta-analysis lead to several suggestions for future research on this topic. The differences in associations between joint attention variables and language (i.e., between RJA and ‘non-RJA’) underscores the need for a clear understanding of the nuances between different joint attention types. Mundy and Jarrold (2010) convincingly argue that IJA and RJA are dissociated constructs in language development, and additional research has examined how other joint attention constructs similarly diverge in their relationship to language (Adamson et al., 2009; Bottema-Beutel et al., 2014). This review could not test differences between all pairs of joint attention constructs because there were too few effect sizes available. Thus, future studies are needed to provide more estimates of CA, and joint engagement states that are measured concurrently with adult linguistic input (i.e., ‘symbol infusion’; Adamson et al., 2009). Future researchers should also remain consistent and careful in their selection and naming of joint attention types. There were several instances in this study where joint attention variables were classified in ways other than the terminology assigned by the researcher (Trautman & Rollins, 2006 for example). Second, isolating the features of joint attention that are most clearly associated with language will help refine developmental research so that only the most crucial aspects are captured in joint attention measures. For example, the summary estimate for SJE was surprisingly low, given studies that have highlighted its importance as a language learning context in comparison to CJE. However, Adamson and colleagues (2009) were careful

to measure this state *along with* parent provision of symbols (i.e., linguistic utterances), which is likely necessary for this state to meaningfully influence language. Further, Bottema-Beutel and colleagues (2014) showed that, at least for children with ASD, refining the SJE state into one that includes reciprocity from the child increased the extent to which this construct was correlated with language, as compared to an SJE state that did not involve child reciprocity. Lastly, as mentioned previously, engagement states may be especially susceptible to unstable estimates (i.e., estimates that vary from session to session). Generalizability and decision studies could be conducted to determine how many measurement sessions are needed to average across in order to generate a stable estimate, which would then yield greater precision when generating correlations with language (Bottema-Beutel et al., 2014).

These results support the increasingly robust evidence that facilitating joint attention is a useful intervention framework for promoting developmentally downstream language. Kasari and colleagues have reported language gains for even minimally verbal children with ASD (who are often outside the reach of current intervention approaches) when joint attention episodes are directly supported within intervention contexts (Kasari et al., 2014). The moderating effect of joint attention on intervention outcomes has also been pointed out, as children who score higher on measures of joint attention acquire greater language gains after intervention (Bono, Daley, & Sigman, 2004). Future work should also examine the mediating effect of joint attention, to further clarify that facilitating joint attention is an ‘active ingredient’ of the intervention.

In closing, this analysis is the first to quantitatively synthesize extant literature on the associations between joint attention and language. Results confirm that the association is in general strong, but can vary according to joint attention type, and between children with ASD and TD children. Future research can further refine our understanding of how joint attention

types differ in their associations with language, and the mechanism by which joint attention leads to language in TD children as compared to children with ASD.

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Conflict of Interest

The author reports that there are no conflicts of interest.

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Figure Legend

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram

*This figure includes effect sizes connected to published reports, but the effect size itself was not published in the report.

Figure 2. Forest plot of effect sizes by language outcome and group. Squares represent summary estimates broken down by joint attention type, and diamonds represent summary estimates collapsed across joint attention types. ASD = Autism Spectrum Disorder, CoA = Coordinated Attention, CJE = Coordinated Joint Engagement, ES = Effect Size, Exp = Expressive Language, IJA = Initiating Joint Attention, JA = Joint Attention, k = number of clusters, n = number of effect sizes, P = Published, Rec = Receptive Language, RJA = Response to Joint Attention, SJE = Supported Joint Engagement, T1 = Time 1, TD = Typically Developing

Table 1

Characteristics of reports included in the meta-analysis

	# of ESs	P/U	Language Variable			ASD				TD			
			Exp	Rec	Comp	<i>n</i>	% male	Age at TI	JA variable	<i>n</i>	% male	Age at TI	JA variable
Adamson et al. (2012)	16	U	X	X		18	87	30.8 [†]	SJE, CJE	53		18.1	SJE, CJE
Benigno et al. (2007)	4	P	X							31	21	20	SJE, CJE
Bono et al. (2004)	4	P			X	29	76	26.4	IJA, RJA				
Bottema-Beutel et al. (2014)	10	P	X	X		63		12.2	SJE				
Carpenter et al. (1998)	68	P	X	X		24	50	9-15	CJE				
Carpenter et al. (2002)	3	P	X			12	92	31.3	IJA, RJA, CoA				
Casenheiser et al. (2015)	1	P	X			51		35.3	IJA				
Charman (2003)	8	P	X	X		18		16.6 ^{††}	RJA, CoA				
Crowson (2001)	1	U	X							44	46	15	RJA
Dawson et al. (2004)	16	P	X	X		72	83	25.2	IJA, RJA				
Delgado et al. (2002)	2	P	X	X						47	47	15	RJA
Dewey (2012)	4	U	X	X						20	50	13	IJA, RJA
Drew et al. (2007) Sample 1	4	P	X	X		17	88	16.4	IJA, RJA				
Drew et al. (2007) Sample 2	4	P				23	91	18.1	IJA, RJA				
Dykstra (2012)	4	U		X		23	92	117.1 [†]	SJE, CJE				
Fiske (2008)	1	U		X		15		48 [†]	CoA				
Frampton (2012)	2	U	X							199	53	19.3	IJA, RJA
Gillespie-Lynch et al. (2012)	7	P			X	18		26.4	IJA, RJA				
Gillespie-Lynch et al. (2015)	36	U	X		X	10	80	11.8-15.7	IJA, RJA	51	26	12.4-18.4	IJA, RJA
Gulsrud et al. (2014)	3	P	X			40		23.9-96.0	IJA, CoA				
Harrop et al. (2015) Sample 1	2	P			X	40	100	26.3	IJA, RJA				
Harrop et al. (2015) Sample 2	2	P			X	39	0	26.1	IJA, RJA				
Henderson (2002)	3	U	X	X						39	36	14	IJA, RJA
Hurwitz & Watson (2015)	2	P			X	20	85	26.2 ^{††}	IJA, RJA				
Hutman (2015)	48	U	X	X		25		12-18	IJA, RJA	124		12-18	IJA, RJA
Kaale et al. (2014)	12	U	X	X		58	24	27.7	IJA, RJA				
Kasari et al. (2008)	4	P	X	X		58	79	24.4	IJA, RJA				
Kuhn (2007)	8	U	X	X		89	80	20.9	IJA, RJA				
Luyster et al. (2008)	4	P	X	X		164	79	18.7	IJA, RJA				

	# of ESs	P/U	Language Variable			ASD				TD			
			Exp	Rec	Comp	<i>n</i>	% male	Age at TI	JA variable	<i>n</i>	% male	Age at TI	JA variable
Maljaars et al. (2011)	4	P	X	X		26	88	39.7	IJA	26	42	35.4	IJA
Markus et al. (2000)	24	P	X	X						21	48	12-18	IJA, RJA, CJE
Martins (2003)	4	U	X	X						30	53	9	IJA, CJE
Martoccio (2010)	1	U	X							139		14	IJA
Matejka (2009)	56	U	X	X						34	56	12.2-18.9	IJA, RJA
Meyer (2002)	1	U			X	54	90	62.5	RJA				
Miller & Marcovitch (2015)	4	P	X	X						47	53	14.4	IJA, RJA
Morales et al. (2000)	26	P	X	X						22	45	6-24	RJA
Mundy & Gomes (1998)	8	P	X	X						24		15.8	IJA, RJA
Mundy et al. (2003)	4	P	X							29	62	14-18	IJA, RJA
Mundy et al. (1990)	1	P			X	15		19.6	IJA				
Park et al. (2011)	6	U	X	X		17	94	22.4	RJA				
Perryman et al. (2013)	2	P		X		37	86	8.02 ^{†††}	IJA, RJA				
Pickard & Ingersoll (2015)	6	P	X	X		53	85	23.5 [†]	IJA, RJA				
Rollins (2003)	3	P	X	X						11	73	12	CJE
Salley & Panneton (2013)	2	P	X	X						52	37	11-14	RJA
Saxon & Reilly (1998)	2	P	X							60	53	25	RJA, SJE
Schietecate et al. (2012)	2	P	X	X		23	78	25.3	IJA				
Schwartz (1999)	2	U	X							51	47	15.1	IJA
Sheinkopf et al. (2012)	1	P	X			15	87	22.1	IJA				
Shumway & Wetherby (2009)	1	P			X	50	86	15.3	IJA				
Sigman & McGovern (2005)	2	P			X	48	88	25	IJA, RJA				
Sigman & Ruskin (1999)	9	P	X	X	X	54		23.7	IJA, RJA	87		19.5	IJA, RJA
Siller & Sigman (2002)	2	P	X		X	17	80	24.2	RJA				
Siller & Sigman (2008)	14	P			X	28	79	25.4 [†]	IJA, RJA				
Slaughter & McConnell (2003)	2	P	X							60	43	11.6	RJA
Smith (2012)	8	U	X	X		19	79	49.7 ^{††}	IJA, RJA	25	36	24	IJA, RJA
Smith (1998)	5	P	X	X	X					137	48	10	IJA
Stone & Yoder (2001)	2	P	X			35	77	17.2	IJA				
Stone & Caro-Martinez (1990)	3	P	X			30	87	51.1	IJA, RJA				
Tek (2010)	1	U	X			9		26.9	RJA				
Tek et al. (2011)	21	U	X	X		17	94	22.4	IJA, RJA, SJE				

	# of ESs	P/U	Language Variable			ASD				TD			
			Exp	Rec	Comp	<i>n</i>	% male	Age at TI	JA variable	<i>n</i>	% male	Age at TI	JA variable
Thorp (2006)	16	U	X	X						76		9-18	IJA, RJA
Toth et al. (2006)	12	P	X	X	X	60	85	25.4	IJA, RJA				
Trautman & Rollins (2006)	1	P	X		X					10	40	12	CoA
Travis et al. (2001)	1	P			X	20	95	80	IJA				
Turner (2005)	4	U	X	X		31	88	18.9	IJA, RJA				
Van der Paelt et al. (2014)	8	P	X	X		51	79	23.6-44.9	IJA, RJA				
Vaughan van Hecke et al. (2007)	6	P	X	X						52	65	12	IJA, RJA
Watson & Baranek (2015)	16	U	X	X		71		28.2	IJA, RJA	48		33.6	IJA, RJA
Watt et al. (2006)	20	P	X	X						160	57	14.3-19.7	IJA, RJA
Wetherby et al. (2012)	4	P	X	X		50	86	21.4 [†]	IJA, RJA				
Williams (2009)	4	U	X	X		16	100	32.6 ^{†††}	RJA	26		39.4	RJA
Yoder et al. (2015)	1	P		X		87	82	12.1	RJA				
Total:	599					1,859				1,835			

Note: All ages are mental age for ASD group and chronological age for TD group, unless indicated as follows. † = Chronological Age, †† = Nonverbal Mental Age, ††† = Verbal Mental Age

ASD = Autism Spectrum Disorder, CoA = Coordinated Attention, CJE = Coordinated Joint Engagement, Comp = Composite Language, ES = Effect Size, Exp = Expressive Language, IJA = Initiating Joint Attention, JA = Joint Attention, P = Published, Rec = Receptive Language, RJA = Response to Joint Attention, SJE = Supported Joint Engagement, T1 = Time 1, TD = Typically Developing, U = Unpublished

Table 2

Means and standard deviations for continuous variables by group and language variable

	ASD			TD		
	Expressive	Receptive	Composite	Expressive	Receptive	Composite
% male	81.25 (16.84)	80.52 (19.28)	78.40 (18.21)	48.38 (9.67)	52.03 (6.27)	32.11 (10.57)
Approx. MA at T1 [†]	24.41 (13.18)	24.58 (16.08)	24.08 (7.01)	15.08 (5.25)	14.79 (5.78)	15.57 (3.28)
Time to Follow-up ^{††}	12.76 (23.54)	5.77 (12.76)	49.05 (68.49)	10.42 (17.53)	5.39 (6.47)	44.41 (35.91)
Year	2010 (5.56)	2010 (4.19)	2008 (5.43)	2005 (6.16)	2005 (6.15)	2008 (0.58)

[†] Chronological age in months for TD children, mental age in months for children with ASD, ^{††} Months between joint attention assessment and language assessment

ASD = Autism Spectrum Disorder, MA = Mental Age, T1= Time 1, TD = Typically Developing

Table 3

Simple regression coefficients and standard errors of moderators by language variable

Moderator	Expressive		Receptive		Composite	
	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE
Group	0.25***	0.066	0.17**	0.06	0.18	0.11
% male	0.005*	0.002	0.004	0.002	-0.001	0.001
Approx. MA at T1 ^{†, ††}	0.30**	0.10	0.10	0.12	.04	0.28
Time to Follow-up (b/w cluster) ^{† †}	0.09	0.07	0.07	0.07	-0.169	0.18
Time to Follow-up (w/in cluster) ^{† †}	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.11	-0.10	0.06
Year	-0.002	0.01	-0.004	0.006	0.001	0.01

† Chronological age in months for TD children, mental age in months for children with ASD, †† Natural log transformed

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$

Coef. = Unstandardized Meta-Regression Coefficient, MA = Mental Age, SE = Standard Error, T1 = Time 1

Table 4

Results of meta-regression analyses by language variable

	Coef.	SE	T ²	<i>k</i>	<i>n</i>
Expressive			0.071	54	332
Group	0.17**	0.06			
Approx. MA at T1	0.21†	0.11			
RJA	0.11†	0.06			
Receptive			0.056	40	209
Group	0.18**	0.06			
RJA	0.13*	0.06			
Composite			0.040	13	66
RJA	0.08	.15			

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, † $p = .07$ (for one tailed test, $p = .035$)

Coef. = Coefficient, *k* = number of studies or 'clusters', *n* = number of effect sizes, MA = Mental Age, RJA = Response to Joint Attention, SE = Standard Error, T² = Tau squared, T1 = Time 1

Figure 1

Figure 2